

Welcome to the first FAME Newsletter!

Find out more about the project, hear from our partners as they make progress on the technological developments of the project, and keep an eye out for upcoming events and opportunities to interact with us and watch us in action!

The FAME Project

Using liquid hydrogen (LH₂) to power fuel cells can eliminate in-flight CO₂, SO_x, and NO_x emissions. Integrating a hydrogen fuel cell propulsion system into a new LH₂-based aircraft design requires moving beyond separate motor and airframe development toward a co-created, fully integrated approach. The FAME project aims to build and demonstrate a compact, multi-megawatt fuel cell propulsion system fuelled by LH₂ for short-range aircraft. Project partners are developing and assembling all necessary subsystems into a ground demonstrator designed for scaling up to an aircraft-level propulsion unit. Close collaboration between subsystem developers and Airbus ensures an optimized design from component materials through overall propulsion integration, setting the stage for a Clean Aviation Phase 2.

Made up of 10 work packages, the FAME project (Grant Agreement: 101140559) is a Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking funded project under the Horizon-Europe framework programme, which kicked-off in January 2025 and has a duration of 36 months. The project is made up of a large consortium, with 21 partners from 7 European countries (Germany, France, Austria, Italy, Poland, Spain and Netherlands), and is a joint effort of 16 companies, 1 research organization and 4 higher education institutions.

Technical project updates

➤ WP3 – Hydrogen Line

Significant advancements have been achieved in the development of the hydrogen storage and distribution system, particularly for potential aircraft use. Our partners at Magna have been leading this effort, achieving several key successes. After constructing and testing the first prototype, in September 2024, the successor Tank has been completed. Figure 1 shows a picture of the Tank with the team that worked on it.

Figure 1. Picture of the Tank along with the team

The tanks performed functional testing campaigns and both tanks have been successfully tested with Liquid Hydrogen (LH2), validating the inner tank, pressurization system, and manufacturing strategy, and confirming their structural integrity, see pictures from LH2 testing below. Figures 2a and 2b illustrate the tank undergoing static tests in roll and pitch jigs, respectively, at flight-representative attitudes.

Figure 2: a) Tank under static functional testing; b) Tank under static functional testing

The advanced prototype tank successfully validated architectural changes and updated/new components, such as improved fill level sensors, a new vacuum architecture, and additional refueling valves.

Additionally, the distribution system has been updated for efficient fluid provision, and the Tank Control Unit (TCU) and Data Acquisition Module (TDAM) have been developed to ensure safe and efficient operation. The first hardware of these control systems is already undergoing testing on the Tank Control Test Bench at Magna facilities in Graz. These advancements collectively pave the way for the final tank system, contributing to the successful implementation of hydrogen storage solutions for future aircraft.

➤ **WP4 – Air Systems Line**

Compressor Preliminary Design:

The propulsion and power team from TU Delft has developed a novel multi-point preliminary design method for centrifugal compressors, implemented in a Python-based in-house software.

Unlike conventional single-point approaches, this multi-point tool developed by TU Delft optimizes the preliminary design at actual operating points determined by the flight mission, utilizing genetic algorithms. This method allows delivering of a preliminary compressor design that is truly tailored to the specific application from the first design steps, significantly reducing the complexity of subsequent design phases. Furthermore, the tool also makes the design process easier, as it allows to select the optimal design point automatically during the optimization itself. Therefore, the optimal design point, that contributes to delivering the highest performance at the specified operating points, is found automatically. The schematic workflow of the tool is shown in Figure 3, that presents the available operating mode, i.e., single-point design, multi-point evaluation, and gradient-free optimization.

Figure 3: Multi-point preliminary design optimization tool schematic

After the validation of the single-point preliminary design mode for the high-pressure ratio NASA High Efficiency Centrifugal Compressor, the tool was used to perform a multi-point preliminary design optimization of the air supply compressor to be utilized for the FAME propulsion system. Figure 4a shows some highlights of the optimization history, particularly, the objective function of the optimization, i.e., total-to-total efficiency –top–; and one of the

constraints, i.e., the maximum blade peripheral speed –bottom. Figure 4b shows the operating map of the optimal compressor, normalized by the mass flow rate at *Ground*, with superposition of design point and three operating points (*Ground*, *Cruise 1* and *Cruise 2*).

Figure 4: a) Multi-point optimization history: total-to-total efficiency –top– and constraint on maximum blade peripheral speed –bottom–; b) optimal compressor operating map, normalized by ground mass flow rate

The comparison of the weighted average performance of the Multi-Point Optimal compressor (MPO) in Figure 4b, against two compressors obtained with Single-Point Optimization (SPO) at the same automatically-identified design point, as well as another SPO performed at design point taken equal to the centre of gravity (CG) of the three operating points, confirmed the highest performance of the MPO compressor, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Weighted-average total-to-total efficiency of the three compressors

CFD solver experimental validation:

To address the subsequent three-dimensional design and optimization of the aerodynamic shape of the FAME air supply compressor, the SU2 flow solver is currently subject to an extensive experimental validation by exploiting the large experimental dataset from the NASA experimental campaign performed on the HECC. The experimental validation considers two sets of data: integral quantities, such as the total-to-total pressure ratio and efficiency along several speedlines; and local quantities, such as static pressure measurements along the hub and shroud of the machine.

Figure 8: CAD Image of experimental humidifier setup - first design

Furthermore, a high-fidelity CFD model a humidifier was developed in *ANSYS Fluent* and part of the measurement data has already been used to perform an initial fitting. The results look promising.

➤ WP6 – Cooling Line

The design phase of the FAME Cooling Line Component has been completed, and the first components have already been manufactured. The equipment is currently being commissioned and prepared for testing. These tests will cover both functional performance against the defined requirements as well as operation under relevant environmental conditions.

In parallel, the air side of the cooling line has been analyzed using high-fidelity numerical simulation using LES. Together with WP2, a cooling duct design was developed to enhance heat transfer performance while minimizing aerodynamic penalties such as pressure loss and flow-induced drag. The investigations also include studies to increase heat release via the nacelle outer surface with fins, while keeping aerodynamic drag low.

Figure 9: System architecture

The ongoing work takes into account the interdependencies between the nacelle's external aerodynamics and the internal flow characteristics. Experimental studies are planned to accompany this work and validate the findings.

➤ **WP7 – Power Line**

The key output and milestone for the Power Line work package has been the design optimisation, build and test of a dual 250kW SiC inverter as shown in Figure 10. This work demonstrates the ability to achieve a compact, high power density inverter package using Silicon Carbide (SiC) power switches. Whilst SiC technology enables the ability to operate at high frequency and a high power density eMotor, it presents a number of challenges. In particular, the power loop design which is the ability to switch the SiC device at high-speed and simultaneously manage the protection of the device in the event of a short circuit.

Figure 10: a) 250kW/400A/20kHz SiC inverter prototype; b) Experimental characterisation

The inverter power loop design was validated through experimental testing, closely matching simulation results. The developed SPICE simulation model successfully predicted short-circuit behavior which is key to aircraft fault protection. Furthermore, it demonstrates the advantage of a sense-diode technique compared to the existing resistive method.

Future work will focus on enhancing the model by better accounting for power module internal parasitic inductances through a novel “black-box” characterization approach. Improvement will also include modelling of reverse recovery effects, the high-voltage/high-current (HV/HC) regions of the Mosfet static curves, and parasitic capacitance to the module baseplate. These enhancements will enable better prediction of inverter behavior, especially regarding conducted Electromagnetic Interference (EMI) over a wide frequency spectrum.

The pursuit of higher power density has led to a strong focus on the inverter thermal design. Studies have shown the clear benefits of liquid cooling and integrated heat pipe solutions. A new system using integrated heat pipes is under development and will be tested shortly, enabling a fair comparison of overall system power density for different cooling strategies.

Figure 11: Inverter current rating versus switching frequency with different thermal management systems

In parallel, work is ongoing to design the highest power density motor at Megawatt power level with a strong focus on the motor cooling scheme. Inverter control optimisation has begun and includes a multi-inverter simulation to study the effect of motor and inverter failure modes and further confirm aircraft safety.

Conclusion

At FAME, our goal is clear: to build and test a multi-megawatt fuel cell propulsion system fuelled by LH2 for short-range aircraft. To this end, we have already developed next-generation liquid-hydrogen tanks and tested them in rigorous roll-and-pitch trials, and have fine-tuned a Python-based compressor design tool that automatically adapts to different flight conditions. Our team has also adapted humidifier rigs to optimize water-vapor levels in fuel cells, finalized the cooling-line hardware now entering its commissioning phase, and produced dual 250 kW power modules that are moving into validation. Next, we will integrate all these subsystems into a 1 MW demonstrator bench to run full-system performance and reliability tests. At the same time, engineers are conducting structural, aerodynamic, and safety checks to satisfy certification standards as well as prove end-to-end propulsion chain. We are also simultaneously creating a digital interface where partners across Europe can share data, designs, lessons learned, and best practices. With these milestones achieved we are inching closer to setting the stage for a Clean Aviation Phase 2.

Published papers

- Mahdavi, N. (2025). Modelling of the Power Demand of Peripheral Aggregates of an Airborne Fuel Cell-Based Power System. *Aerospace*, 12(3), 234. <https://doi.org/10.3390/aerospace12030234>

Upcoming publications

- Capiello A.; Ciaï V.; Pini M.: *A multi-point preliminary design method for centrifugal compressor stages of fuel cell-based propulsion systems*. **Proceedings ETC 2025, 2025.**
- Capiello A.; Ciaï V.; Pini M.: *A multi-point preliminary design method for centrifugal compressor stages of fuel cell-based propulsion systems*. (submitted to **International Journal of Turbomachinery, Propulsion and Power**)
- Sotomayor-Zakharov, D., Scholz, P.: *Numerical parametric analysis of finned surfaces for enhanced cooling*, **Proceedings of EUCASS 2025, 2025.**
- Sotomayor-Zakharov, D., Scholz, P.: *A cooling approach for a fuel cell aircraft engine using finned surfaces*. **Proceedings of EUCASS 2025, 2025.**
- Singh, P., Schmidt, N. F., Merbold, S., Rudnik, R., de Graaf, S.: *Numerical investigation of unsteady fluid flow inside air cooling lines with tilted heat exchanger for electrified aero engines*. **Proceedings or special-issue of EASN 2025, 2025**
- Salloukh A.; Tounzi A.; Nguyen N.K.; Prieto D.; McClelland M.: *Calcul analytique de l'induction d'armature d'une machine électrique à aimants en surface*. **Proceedings of SGE 2025, 2025.**

Past events

The FAME consortium is very active in various conferences like ETC, EASN, EUCASS and the Air Shows. Our colleagues also joined the AIAA SciTech and Aviation Forums this year, as well as local conferences like the Electrical Engineering Symposium (SGE2025) in France and the Conference of Basic Problems of Metrology (PPM2025) in Poland. We were also invited by Clean Aviation to present a poster and the ZEROe propulsion system model at the Clean Aviation Annual Forum in Brussels in March 2025. Consortium members recently also participated in prominent events such as DLRK 2025 and the SU2 Conference, delivering presentations and contributing to potential conference proceedings. They will continue to share their findings at upcoming events in the near future.

Upcoming conferences and presentations

We are excited to share that our project will be represented at several leading conferences in the coming months. Below you can find an overview of our contributions:

[EASN Conference 2025](#)

14 Oct – 17 Oct
Madrid, Spain

Presentations:

“Numerical investigation of unsteady fluid flow inside air cooling lines with tilted heat exchanger for electrified aero engines” — DLR

DLR STAB-Workshop 2025

10 Nov – 12 Nov
Göttingen, Germany

Presentation:

- *“LES/URANS of heat transfer enhancement due to Kelvin-Helmholtz instability on finned channel”* — TU Braunschweig

We look forward to exchanging ideas with the community. If you are attending any of these events, come meet us!

Follow us on [LinkedIn](#) for more updates on our journey towards a future of aviation that significantly reduces greenhouse-gas emissions compared to today's jet engine!